

Almohads (al-Muwaḥḥidūn)

also known as "Almohadism"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, African Religions, Apocalyptic Movements, Amazigh, African Religion, North African Religion, Islamic Traditions, Hispano-Islamic

The Almohads (al-Muwaḥḥidūn; "the monotheists") were a Muslim sectarian movement that formed around Muḥammad ibn Tūmart (ca. 1080-1130), a Moroccan religious scholar who claimed to be an "infallible leader" (imām ma'ṣūm) and "the acknowledged mahdī" (al-mahdī al-ma'lūm). Although raised within a Sunnī milieu, Ibn Tūmart emphasized his infallible leadership and messianic role (i.e. the mahdī) to such an extent that Almohadism became a branch of Islam distinct from Sunnism, Shī'ism, and Khārījism/Ibāḍism.

Date Range: 1115 CE - 1269 CE

Region: Almohad North Africa and Iberia

Region tags: Africa, Spain, Portugal, al-Andalus, North Africa, Iberia, Tunisia, Morocco, Western Sahara, Algeria, Libya

The Almohad Caliphate at its greatest extent (ca. 1180-1212)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ibn Tūmart, Muḥammad b. 'Abdallāh. *A'azz mā yuṭlab*. Edited by 'Ammār Ṭālibī. Algiers: al-Mu'assasa al-Waṭaniyya li-l-Kitāb, 1985. [Algiers: 'Aṣima al-Thaqāfa al-'Arabiyya, 2007.]
- Source 2: Al-Baydhaq, Abū Bakr b. 'Alī al-Ṣanhājī. *Akḥbār al-mahdī*. Edited by 'Abd al-Wahhāb b. Maṣṣūr. Rabat: Dār al-Manṣūr, 1971.
- Source 3: Fromherz, Allen J. *The Almohads: The Rise of an Islamic Empire*. Reprint edition. London: I.B.Tauris, 2012.

Notes: See also García Arenal, Mercedes. *Messianism and Puritanical Reform: Mahdīs of the Muslim West*. Leiden: Brill, 2006.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-2/al-muwahhidun-COM_0824?s.num=2&s.f.s2_parent=s.f.book.encyclopaedia-of-islam-2&s.q=almohads
- Source 1 Description: Shatzmiller, M., "al-Muwaḥḥidūn", in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition*, Edited by: P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs.

- Source 2 URL: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-2/ibn-tumart-SIM_3395?s.num=0&s.f.s2_parent=s.f.book.encyclopaedia-of-islam-2&s.q=ibn+tumart
 - Source 2 Description: Hopkins, J.F.P., “Ibn Tūmart”, in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, Second Edition, Edited by: P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs.
 - Source 3 URL: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-3/almohads-COM_23952?s.num=0&s.f.s2_parent=s.f.book.encyclopaedia-of-islam-3&s.q=almohads
 - Source 3 Description: Viguera Molins, Maria Jesús, “Almohads”, in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, THREE, Edited by: Kate Fleet, Gudrun Krämer, Denis Matringe, John Nawas, Devin J. Stewart.
- Notes: See also: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopaedia-of-islam-3/ibn-tumart-COM_32275?s.num=0&s.f.s2_parent=s.f.book.encyclopaedia-of-islam-3&s.q=ibn+tumart Ghouirgate, Mehdi, “Ibn Tūmart”, in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, THREE, Edited by: Kate Fleet, Gudrun Krämer, Denis Matringe, John Nawas, Devin J. Stewart.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b8419211m?rk=21459;2>
- Source 1 Description: Ibn Tūmart, Muḥammad. *Sifr fī-hi jāmi’ ta’ālīq al-imām al-ma’šūm al-mahdī al-ma’lūm mim mā amlāhu sayyidunā al-imām al-khalīfa amīr al-mu’minīn Abū Muḥammad ‘Abd al-Mu’min b. ‘Alī*. Ms. Paris, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, fonds arabe 1451.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Almohads regarded the writings of Ibn Tūmart as canonical. As Muslims, however, they still believed the Qur’ān to be revealed by God to Muḥammad (sometimes through the mediation of the archangel Gabriel/Jibrīl) and, therefore, the holiest and

most authoritative text in their canon.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: As above, Almohad Muslims believed that God's revelation of the Qur'ān to Muḥammad sometimes occurred through the mediation of the angel Gabriel/Jibrīl.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Islam often speaks of divine revelation in terms of "inspiration" (wa'ī).

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Certain aspects of Almohad theology and law, whether they are transmitted orally or in writing, are believed to derive from Ibn Tūmart's unique relationship to God as the infallible imām and mahdī.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: During the period of the Almohad Caliphate's ascendancy (1147-1269), the Almohads ruled over a multi-ethnic empire. The majority of the Almohad Caliphate's inhabitants were Sunnī Muslims, though there were significant numbers of Jews, Latin and Mozarabic Christians, and adherents of traditional North African religions. The uniqueness of the Almohads' Islamic identity prompted them to pressure both non-Muslims and Sunnī Muslims to convert to Almohadism. Following the collapse of the Almohad Caliphate in 1269, many religious Almohads continued to practice their faith under Sunnī rule (often clandestinely) or enjoyed relative tolerance, as in the Almohad successor state of Ḥafṣīd Tunisia.

Reference: Cornell, Vincent. "Faḳīh Versus Faḳīr in Marinid Morocco: Epistemological Dimensions of Polemic". In *Islamic Mysticism Contested: Thirteen Centuries of Controversies and Polemics*. Leiden: Brill, 1999.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Since Muslims populations subject to the Almohad state were often considered to have assented to Almohad Islam by default, it is difficult to distinguish nominal Almohads from the "true believers."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Reference: Buresi, Pascal. "Les Cultes Rendus À La Tombe Du Mahdí Ibn Tūmart À Tinmâl (xiie-xiiiie S.)". *Comptes-rendus Des Séances De L Année - Académie Des Inscriptions Et Belles- Lettres* 152 1 (2008): 391-438.

Reference: Balbale, Abigail Krasner. "Affiliation and Ideology at the End of the Almohad Caliphate". *Al-masāq* 30, no. 3 (September 2, 2018): 266-83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09503110.2018.1525241>.

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: The tombs of Ibn Tūmart and the Almohad caliphs in Tīnmall (now southern Morocco) became the focus of an annual "visitation" (ziyāra) by the caliph's retinue and army. The first caliph, 'Abd al-Mu'min, appears to have intended the ziyāra as a rival to (or even a replacement of) the Ḥajj pilgrimage to Mecca.

↳ Cemeteries:

– I don't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Fortresses, such as the one at Tinmel, took on religious significance due to their role

in the propagation of Almohad Islam and the expansion of the Almohad empire.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Reference: Balbale, Abigail Krasner. "Affiliation and Ideology at the End of the Almohad Caliphate". *Al-masāq* 30, no. 3 (September 2, 2018): 266–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09503110.2018.1525241>.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– I don't know

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– I don't know

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Almohad Caliphate (1130-1269) provided political support for Almohadism and funded its missionary (da'wa) efforts. In the early Almohad period, the Almohad Caliphate and its religious institutions are virtually indistinguishable. Biographical descriptions of the religiosity of the Mu'minid Caliphs shows a steady decline in belief in the tenets unique to Almohadism—perhaps owing to the fact

that the caliphal family entrusted their sons' educations to Sunnī scholars. The Almohad Caliph al-Ma'mūn formally repudiated belief in Ibn Tūmart's infallibility (the cornerstone of Almohadism) in 1230. Despite this, the hard core of the Almohad movement continued to uphold their distinct beliefs and practices without state support.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: As the imām and mahdī, Ibn Tūmart wielded religious and political authority until his death in 1130. The first Almohad caliph, 'Abd al-Mu'min, appealed to the Islamic concept of khilāfa (vice-regency; succession to the Prophet Muḥammad) to arrogate this dual authority to himself. Although all Almohad caliphs until 1269 would claim political authority, many later caliphs privately doubted their religious authority (imāma). In 1230, the caliph al-Ma'mūn officially repudiated belief in Ibn Tūmart's infallibility, implicitly denying his own right, as Almohad caliph, to adjudicate infallibly.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: García Arenal, Mercedes. *Messianism and Puritanical Reform: Mahdīs of the Muslim West*. Leiden: Brill, 2006.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque-fortress and mausoleum at Tinmel (Tīnmall) in the High Atlas mountains became the center of Almohad devotion to Ibn Tūmart and the Almohad caliphs. The first Almohad caliph, ‘Abd al-Mu’min, instituted an annual pilgrimage (ziyāra) to Tinmel. It is possible that this pilgrimage to Ibn Tūmart's grave was intended to rival or even replace the Ḥajj pilgrimage to Mecca.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: The major Almohad festival was the annual pilgrimage (ziyāra) to Ibn Tūmart's tomb. The Almohad caliphs led these pilgrimages and used them as occasions to gather representatives from across the Almohads' burgeoning empire and bestow political appointments.

Membership/Group Interactions

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Size and Structure

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Architecture, Geography

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Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: The killing of non-Almohads and non-Muslims depends on circumstances. The killing of religious enemies in jihād was permissible if these enemies resisted conquest and conversion. However, if the enemies capitulated by accepting a pact of "safety" (amān), the Almohads dealt with them magnanimously. Even in the case of conquered non-Muslim populations, the Almohads were more tolerant to those who accepted amān rather than fighting back.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Yes [specify]: Adherence to Islam as interpreted by Ibn Tūmart

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Almohad social norms derived from Ibn Tūmart's rather strict interpretation of Islamic Law (sharī'a). In addition to Islamic Law, the Almohad Caliphate possessed a set of norms governing the military, the caliph's household, and the scholars (ṭalaba) responsible for the propagation of Almohad doctrine and the pursuit of the arts and sciences.

Reference: Fierro, Maribel. "The Religious Policy of the Almohads". In *The Oxford Handbook of Islamic Theology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. "Almohad Tawḥīd and Its Implications for Religious Difference". *Journal of Medieval Iberian Studies* 2, no. 2 (2010): 195-216.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Messianism is at the heart of Almohad Islam. Ibn Tūmart claimed to be the awaited Mahdī, a messiah figure spoken of in ḥadīth literature. As the Mahdī, Ibn Tūmart believed himself to be a recapitulation of the Prophet Muḥammad with the ability to create sunna (i.e. to establish ritual and legal practices which are included as part of revelation) and equal authority over the global Muslim community (umma).

Reference: García Arenal, Mercedes. *Messianism and Puritanical Reform: Mahdīs of the Muslim West*. Leiden: Brill, 2006.

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: Ibn Tūmart was staunchly opposed to anthropomorphism or corporealism (tajsīm) in theology.

Reference: Bourouiba, Rachid. "La Doctrine Almohade" 13, no. 1 (1973).
<https://doi.org/10.3406/remmm.1973.1199>.

Reference: Brunschvig, Robert. "Sur La Doctrine Du Mahdi Ibn Tūmart". *Arabica* 2, no. 2 (1955): 137–49.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: The Almohad caliphs based their authority on Ibn Tūmart's claim to be the Mahdī, a messianic re-capitulation of the prophet Muḥammad. As in many theories of Islamic leadership, the authority of Muḥammad stems from his relationship to God as prophet.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omniscience, omnipotence, absolute unity and transcendence

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: knowledge of the unseen (al-ghayb)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– No

Notes: According to Ibn Tūmart's strict monotheism, God does not express emotion, since emotion implies change in Him and, therefore, disunity and resemblance to created beings. However, the Qur'ān frequently speaks of God as displaying both positive and negative emotions like love and anger.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: In Islam, God can and does communicate with human beings by revealing scriptures to prophets (anbiyā') and messengers (rusul).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Although the Almohads, like other Muslims, do not restrict God's power of communication (He is, after all, omnipotent), they see God as delivering privileged messages or non-verbal inspiration to past prophets (especially Muḥammad), Ibn Tūmart, and the Almohad Caliphs.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a history of belief in spirits in Morocco among Muslims, but Almohad sources do

not specify the movement's position on human spirits or ghosts.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to God (Allāh), the Almohads—like the vast majority of Muslims—believed in angels and jinn. It is not certain whether the Almohads accepted the existence of other supernatural beings.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The angel Gabriel (Jibrīl) is credited with delivering all or most of the Qur'ān to the prophet Muḥammad.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Like most Muslims, the Almohads believe in an afterlife which consists in bodily resurrection, judgment, and reward and punishment. In "The Creed of the Almohads" ('Aqīdat al-muwaḥḥidīn), Ibn Tūmart cites a prophetic ḥadīth from Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim (1: 10: 43): "Whoever dies knowing that there is no god but God enters the garden." He interprets this statement to mean that salvation is contingent upon one's intellectual knowledge of God's unity.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ibn Tūmart goes to great lengths to distinguish revealed norms (i.e. those set down by God, Muḥammad, or Muḥammad's Companions) and merely conventional norms. To put a conventional norm on par with divine law is an act of unbelief (kufr) or association (shirk). Customary norms, though beneficial for human survival and flourishing, are by no means morally obligatory precisely because they do not derive from God.

Reference: Brunschvig, Robert. "Sur La Doctrine Du Mahdi Ibn Tūmart". *Arabica* 2, no. 2 (1955): 137-49.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For Ibn Tūmart and the Almohads, moral norms are exactly coextensive with the norms of Islamic law (sharī'a). Islamic law derives from the will of God who is personal, but not anthropomorphic.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Although the norms of Islamic law apply to all human beings at all times, Ibn Tūmart enumerates several factors which reduce or eliminate moral culpability, including maturity, mental soundness, and knowledge of revelation.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: While the Almohads certainly attribute punishment and reward to God, it is unclear whether they also attribute punishment and reward to lesser supernatural beings like angels and demons.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Most divine punishment is relegated to the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: While Almohads ultimately attribute reward and punishment to God, it is not clear whether they also attribute agency in reward and punishment to lesser beings like angels and demons.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See above.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Like the Ash'arī school of Sunnī theology, the Almohads conceived of eternal happiness as the "vision" (ru'ya) of God Himself.
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Almohad Muslims likely followed burial customs comparable to those of Sunnīs in North Africa and Iberia. However, the body of Ibn Tūmart and the bodies of the caliphs were accorded pride of place in the mausoleum at Tinmel. Visitation to Ibn Tūmart's tomb, in particular, was thought to confer a blessing (baraka) and was associated with the performance of minor miracles (karāmāt).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: The tomb of Ibn Tūmart by the mosque at Tinmel

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Like most Muslims, the Almohads believe in an afterlife which consists in bodily resurrection, judgment, and reward and punishment. In "The Creed of the Almohads" ('Aqīdat al-muwaḥḥidīn), Ibn Tūmart cites a prophetic ḥadīth from Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim (I: 10: 43): "Whoever dies knowing that there is no god but God enters the garden." He interprets this statement to mean that salvation is contingent upon one's intellectual knowledge of God's unity.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Almohad Muslims likely followed burial customs comparable to those of Sunnīs in North Africa and Iberia. However, the body of Ibn Tūmart and the bodies of the caliphs were accorded pride of place in the mausoleum at Tinmel. Visitation to Ibn Tūmart's tomb, in particular, was thought to confer a blessing (baraka) and was associated with the performance of minor miracles (karāmāt).

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↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: The tomb of Ibn Tūmart by the mosque at Tinmel

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: Ibn Tūmart was staunchly opposed to anthropomorphism or corporealism (tajsīm) in theology.

Reference: Bourouiba, Rachid. "La Doctrine Almohade" 13, no. 1 (1973).
<https://doi.org/10.3406/remmm.1973.1199>.

Reference: Brunschvig, Robert. "Sur La Doctrine Du Mahdi Ibn Tūmart". *Arabica* 2, no. 2 (1955): 137-49.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Yes [specify]: The Almohad caliphs based their authority on Ibn Tūmart's claim to be the Mahdī, a messianic re-capitulation of the prophet Muḥammad. As in many theories of Islamic leadership, the authority of Muḥammad stems from his relationship to God as prophet.
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Omniscience, omnipotence, absolute unity and transcendence
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: knowledge of the unseen (al-ghayb)
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– No

Notes: According to Ibn Tūmart's strict monotheism, God does not express emotion, since emotion implies change in Him and, therefore, disunity and resemblance to created beings. However, the Qur'ān frequently speaks of God as displaying both positive and negative emotions like love and anger.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: In Islam, God can and does communicate with human beings by revealing scriptures to prophets (anbiyā') and messengers (rusul).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Although the Almohads, like other Muslims, do not restrict God's power of communication (He is, after all, omnipotent), they see God as delivering privileged messages or non-verbal inspiration to past prophets (especially Muḥammad), Ibn Tūmart, and the Almohad Caliphs.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is a history of belief in spirits in Morocco among Muslims, but Almohad sources do not specify the movement's position on human spirits or ghosts.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to God (Allāh), the Almohads—like the vast majority of Muslims—believed in angels and jinn. It is not certain whether the Almohads accepted the existence of other supernatural beings.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: The angel Gabriel (Jibrīl) is credited with delivering all or most of the Qur'ān to the prophet Muḥammad.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

- No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

- Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically:

- Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

- Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including

obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: The killing of non-Almohads and non-Muslims depends on circumstances. The killing of religious enemies in jihād was permissible if these enemies resisted conquest and conversion. However, if the enemies capitulated by accepting a pact of "safety" (amān), the Almohads dealt with them magnanimously. Even in the case of conquered non-Muslim populations, the Almohads were more tolerant to those who accepted amān rather than fighting back.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: Adherence to Islam as interpreted by Ibn Tūmart

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: While the Almohads certainly attribute punishment and reward to God, it is unclear whether they also attribute punishment and reward to lesser supernatural beings like angels and demons.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Most divine punishment is relegated to the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No

Notes: While Almohads ultimately attribute reward and punishment to God, it is not clear whether they also attribute agency in reward and punishment to lesser beings like angels and demons.

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: See above.

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Like the Ash'arī school of Sunnī theology, the Almohads conceived of eternal happiness as the "vision" (ru'ya) of God Himself.
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Messianism is at the heart of Almohad Islam. Ibn Tūmart claimed to be the awaited Mahdī, a messiah figure spoken of in ḥadīth literature. As the Mahdī, Ibn Tūmart believed himself to be a recapitulation of the Prophet Muḥammad with the ability to create sunna (i.e. to establish ritual and legal practices which are included as part of revelation) and equal authority over the global Muslim community (umma).

Reference: García Arenal, Mercedes. *Messianism and Puritanical Reform: Mahdīs of the Muslim West*. Leiden: Brill, 2006.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Almohad social norms derived from Ibn Tūmart's rather strict interpretation of Islamic Law (sharī'a). In addition to Islamic Law, the Almohad Caliphate possessed a set of norms governing the military, the caliph's household, and the scholars (ṭalaba) responsible for the propagation of Almohad doctrine and the pursuit of the arts and sciences.

Reference: Fierro, Maribel. "The Religious Policy of the Almohads". In *The Oxford Handbook of Islamic Theology*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. "Almohad Tawḥīd and Its Implications for Religious Difference". *Journal of Medieval Iberian Studies* 2, no. 2 (2010): 195–216.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ibn Tūmart goes to great lengths to distinguish revealed norms (i.e. those set down by God, Muḥammad, or Muḥammad's Companions) and merely conventional norms. To put a conventional norm on par with divine law is an act of unbelief (kufr) or association (shirk). Customary norms, though beneficial for human survival and flourishing, are by no means morally obligatory precisely because they do not derive from God.

Reference: Brunschvig, Robert. "Sur La Doctrine Du Mahdi Ibn Tūmart". *Arabica* 2, no. 2 (1955): 137–49.

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For Ibn Tūmart and the Almohads, moral norms are exactly coextensive with the norms of Islamic law (sharī'a). Islamic law derives from the will of God who is personal, but not anthropomorphic.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Although the norms of Islamic law apply to all human beings at all times, Ibn Tūmart enumerates several factors which reduce or eliminate moral culpability, including maturity, mental soundness, and knowledge of revelation.

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: As in other branches of Islam, Almohadism places constraints on sexual activity that does not occur within a marriage contracted according to Islamic Law. It also appears that Almohad warriors would engage in voluntary abstinence during campaigns. Ibn Tūmart himself never married and lived as a celibate. The reason for his celibacy is not known.

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Muslims, the Almohads fasted during the month of Ramaḍān and observed supererogatory fasts for spiritual benefit.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Proscribed food and drink include pork and alcohol (even medicinal use).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Male circumcision

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Ibn Tūmart and the Almohad caliphs frequently required Almohad Muslims to contribute property and labor to aid in jihād.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Males are required to engage in military jihād if necessary.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: After the collapse of the Almohad Caliphate in 1269, Almohad Muslims no longer enjoyed ascendant status in North Africa and Iberia. Sunnī Muslims condemned many distinguishing features of Almohad Islam, such as belief in Ibn Tūmart's status as the Mahdī.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. "Almohad Tawḥīd and Its Implications for Religious Difference". *Journal of Medieval Iberian Studies* 2, no. 2 (2010): 195–216.

Reference: Balbale, Abigail Krasner. "Affiliation and Ideology at the End of the Almohad Caliphate". *Al-masāq* 30, no. 3 (September 2, 2018): 266–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09503110.2018.1525241>.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale rituals include daily prayers in a mosque (ṣalāh), Friday congregational prayer (ṣalāt al-jumu'a), and the annual pilgrimage (ziyāra) to Tinmel.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Notes: Many Amazigh tribes have customarily used tattoos as markers of group identity. As a rather puritanical Islamic movement, the Almohads would have discouraged or forbidden this traditional because Islamic law forbids tattoos and similar body modifications. Since the majority of the early Almohad movement came from a variety of Amazigh tribes, it is quite possible that many Almohad Muslims acquired tattoos prior to their adherence to the movement or continued the practice despite official condemnation.

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Women were required to cover their hair according to Islamic law. The Almohads were vociferous in their enforcement of laws regarding head coverings because their predecessors and enemies, the Almoravids, continued to follow the pre-Islamic customs of the Ṣanhāja/Znaga Amazigh peoples from the Saharan regions of Africa. Ṣanhāja freewomen did not cover their hair in public, whereas Ṣanhāja freemen wore head coverings and, sometimes, mouth coverings. Ibn Tūmart's biographer, al-Baydhaq, portrays the Almoravids as perpetrating an inversion of Islamic gender roles.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: The Almohads used the Atlas dialect of the Tamazight language (comparable to modern Tashelhit in Morocco) in public rituals. Ibn Tūmart and the "hard core" of Almohad Islam spoke this dialect natively. The use of a non-Arabic language in Islamic ritual prayer scandalized some Muslims.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: As in other branches of Islam, Almohadism places constraints on sexual activity that does not occur within a marriage contracted according to Islamic Law. It also appears that Almohad warriors would engage in voluntary abstinence during campaigns. Ibn Tūmart himself never married and lived as a celibate. The reason for his celibacy is not known.

Monogamy (males):

– No

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Muslims, the Almohads fasted during the month of Ramaḍān and observed supererogatory fasts for spiritual benefit.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Proscribed food and drink include pork and alcohol (even medicinal use).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Male circumcision

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Ibn Tūmart and the Almohad caliphs frequently required Almohad Muslims to contribute property and labor to aid in jihād.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Males are required to engage in military jihād if necessary.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: After the collapse of the Almohad Caliphate in 1269, Almohad Muslims no longer enjoyed ascendant status in North Africa and Iberia. Sunnī Muslims condemned many distinguishing features of Almohad Islam, such as belief in Ibn Tūmart's status as the Mahdī.

Reference: Bennison, Amira K.. "Almohad Tawḥīd and Its Implications for Religious Difference". *Journal of Medieval Iberian Studies* 2, no. 2 (2010): 195–216.

Reference: Balbale, Abigail Krasner. "Affiliation and Ideology at the End of the Almohad Caliphate". *Al-masāq* 30, no. 3 (September 2, 2018): 266–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09503110.2018.1525241>.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Large-scale rituals include daily prayers in a mosque (ṣalāh), Friday congregational prayer (ṣalāt al-jumu'a), and the annual pilgrimage (ziyāra) to Tinmel.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

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↳ Hair:

– Yes

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↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: The Almohads used the Atlas dialect of the Tamazight language (comparable to modern Tashelḥit in Morocco) in public rituals. Ibn Tūmart and the "hard core" of Almohad Islam spoke this dialect natively. The use of a non-Arabic language in Islamic ritual prayer scandalized some Muslims.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The Almohad Caliphate was an empire. Originally, the Almohad movement mobilized members of Ibn Tūmart's native Maṣmūda tribal confederation against another Amazigh confederation, the Ṣanhāja, who formed the elite class of the Almoravid empire.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Almohad elite was called "the Students" (al-ṭalaba), referring to their original role as the pupils and disciples of Ibn Tūmart. The ṭalaba developed into an elaborate system. In addition to the council of Ten (whose leader was the caliph himself) there were the Fifty and the Seventy. In documents, we notice a distinction between "the Students of the Almohads" (ṭalabat al-muwaḥḥidīn) and "the Students of the [Caliphal] Court" (ṭalabat al-ḥaḍar). The former were likely Almohad "true believers" drawn from elite Maṣmūda families; the latter were made up of Sunnī scholars and literati (many from elite Iberian families) whom the Almohads wanted to bring into the movement by inviting them to the court in

Marrakesh. The ṭalaba not only advised the caliph, but likewise participated in public discussions, debates, and poetry readings. In addition to the ṭalaba, the Almohad military employed "memorizers" (ḥuffāẓ) who would learn Almohad doctrine from the ṭalaba and transmit it orally to the corners of the Almohad empire.

Reference: Fricaud, Émile. "Les Ṭalaba Dans La Société Almohade". *Al-qanṭara* 18, no. 2 (1997): 331-87.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Although not as extensive as modern police forces, the Almohads, like other Muslim polities, appointed men to serve as muḥtasib or "market inspector." The muḥtasib not only enforced fair standards in trade, but also made sure that Muslims and visiting non-Muslims observed Islamic Law in public.

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Since the early Almohads pertained to the Maṣmūda tribal confederation, the Almohads obtained food according to pre-existing customs—especially pastoralism. As a large empire, the Almohads supported and benefited from large-scale agricultural production. After the collapse of the Almohad Caliphate, some Almohads are reported to have considered meat slaughtered by Sunnī Muslims to be illicit.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

- Yes

Notes: In addition to classical Arabic, the Almohad Caliphate used a dialect of Tamazight native to the High Atlas region in religious rituals, the caliphal court, and as in literature (written and oral). Unfortunately, we do not possess Tamazight texts from this period, though they are mentioned in Arabic sources.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

- Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: Almohad Muslims in coastal North Africa and Iberia would certainly have traded foodstuffs and other goods with neighboring countries.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

- Yes

Notes: Other non-Almohad institutions of learning, especially mosque and house schools continued. Muslims from Almohad lands also travelled abroad to receive education in the Islamic East, just as Ibn Tūmart did in the early 6th/12th century.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Although the Almohads introduced annual ritual observances like the pilgrimage to Tinmel, they retained the basic structure of the Islamic calendar and observed common Muslim holidays like the Ramaḍān fast.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The dialect of Tamazight spoken by Ibn Tūmart, though used in ritual texts, did not displace Arabic as a religious language. Almohad presence in Iberia suggests that some Almohad Muslims may have spoken a Romance language as a first or second language. Almohad diplomatic missions to Latin Europe indicates that a small number of Almohad elites acquired knowledge of literary Latin and relevant vernacular languages.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If Almohad Muslims travelled abroad for extensive periods of time—especially to Christian Europe—
–they would have been subject to local laws and courts.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Almohad Muslims traveling or living abroad would have been subject to other legal codes.

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The Almohad Caliphate was an empire. Originally, the Almohad movement mobilized members of Ibn Tūmart's native Mašmūda tribal confederation against another Amazigh confederation, the Ṣanhāja, who formed the elite class of the Almoravid empire.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Almohad elite was called "the Students" (al-ṭalaba), referring to their original role as the pupils and disciples of Ibn Tūmart. The ṭalaba developed into an elaborate system. In addition to the council of Ten (whose leader was the caliph himself) there were the Fifty and the Seventy. In documents, we notice a distinction between "the Students of the Almohads" (ṭalabat al-muwaḥḥidīn) and "the Students of the [Caliphal] Court" (ṭalabat al-ḥaḍar). The former were likely Almohad "true believers" drawn from elite Mašmūda families; the latter were made up of Sunnī scholars and literati (many from elite Iberian families) whom the Almohads wanted to bring into the movement by inviting them to the court in Marrakesh. The ṭalaba not only advised the caliph, but likewise participated in public discussions, debates, and poetry readings. In addition to the ṭalaba, the Almohad military employed "memorizers" (ḥuffāz) who would learn Almohad doctrine from the ṭalaba and transmit it orally to the corners of the Almohad empire.

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Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Other non-Almohad institutions of learning, especially mosque and house schools continued. Muslims from Almohad lands also travelled abroad to receive education in the Islamic East, just as Ibn Tūmart did in the early 6th/12th century.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: Although not as extensive as modern police forces, the Almohads, like other Muslim polities, appointed men to serve as muḥtasib or "market inspector." The muḥtasib not only enforced fair standards in trade, but also made sure that Muslims and visiting non-Muslims observed Islamic Law in

public.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

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↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

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the religious group in question:

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Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

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Notes: In addition to classical Arabic, the Almohad Caliphate used a dialect of Tamazight native to the High Atlas region in religious rituals, the caliphal court, and as in literature (written and oral). Unfortunately, we do not possess Tamazight texts from this period, though they are mentioned in Arabic sources.

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Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Although the Almohads introduced annual ritual observances like the pilgrimage to Tinmel, they retained the basic structure of the Islamic calendar and observed common Muslim holidays like the Ramaḡān fast.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Since the early Almohads pertained to the Maṣmūda tribal confederation, the Almohads obtained food according to pre-existing customs—especially pastoralism. As a large empire, the Almohads supported and benefited from large-scale agricultural production. After the collapse of the Almohad Caliphate, some Almohads are reported to have considered meat slaughtered by Sunnī Muslims to be illicit.

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